

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF JAZZ HISTORY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article provides information about the stages of development of the Jazz music genre in Uzbekistan, the period of its formation. Also, there are opinions about the process of emergence of jazz music in the art of music.

Keywords: music, jazz, education, creativity, ability, musician, instrument, pedagogy, festival, style, talent, individuality, art.

Musical variety is a means of actively developing emotional feelings that quickly affect a person. It is known that by getting to know music, you can enjoy music for a lifetime. In general, music is an integral part of the human psyche. Music is an art form that occupies a large place in our cultural life and plays an important role in the development of human personality.

In music, the Jazz genre teaches to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around. Music equips a person with high taste, shapes his spiritual outlook. This system has the ability to strongly influence human feelings and is an important means of introducing students to the world of sophistication and moral education.¹

First of all, let's talk about the **Jazz genre**. Jazz (*English: jazz*) is a type of professional music, one of the main stylistic sources of modern popular, especially pop music. In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the elements of African and European musical culture merged together, resulting in the work of African-Americans from New Orleans, Louisiana, USA. The signs of the folklore of the African peoples - the sounding of different methods, the repetition of the main melody that changes almost every time, the richness of the original laments, the exciting singing style, the performance art of a certain direction - have become the basic characteristics of Jazz.²

Initially, the pieces created and performed by the members of the ensemble consisting of 7-8 musicians were called jazz or "jazzband". Jazz founders L.S.

¹ Avdeeva L. From the history of Uzbek national dance // Gafur Gulom Publishing House of Literature and Art. - Tashkent, 2014. - B

² "Jazz Origins in New Orleans – New Orleans Jazz National Historical Park". National Park Service.

Armstrong, J.K. Oliver, J. Dode, E.K. Ori, J.R. Morton and others were the leaders of such ensembles. Later, following them, Dixieland groups appeared and promoted the art of Jazz in America and Europe. In the 1930s, "swing" (D. Ellington, U.K. Basie) and other styles emerged, large Jazz orchestras were formed. B. Goodman, G. Miller and J. Coltrane (USA), J. Dankworth (England), M. Legrand (France), K. Vlach and G. Brom (Czechoslovakia), K. Edelhagen (Germany), K. Komeda (Poland), A. Sfasmanlar toured with his orchestra in Tashkent in 1962.³

Jazz music began to appear in Uzbekistan in the second half of the 1940s. Music ensembles under the leadership of D. Sokolov, A. Pozdnyakov, M. Azatyan and others performed samples of jazz and pop music in cinemas, palaces of culture, and city parks of cities such as Tashkent, Samarkand, Fergana, Andijan. In 1958, the formation of the Pop Orchestra of Uzbekistan, and in 1963, the formation of Pop Symphony Orchestras under Uzteleradio, gave impetus to the development of jazz. A. Kroll, A. Malakhov, Ye. The contribution of conductors like Zhivayev was significant. "Namangan's apple" (Sh. Ramazonov), "Kiz bola" (E. Solihov) reworked versions of the songs in jazz style, "Yulduz circle", "Black eyes" orchestral works written using Uzbek melody and methods by A. Malakhov are the first national jazz music. is one of the examples.⁴

Jazz music also developed in the later period. In 1968, the 1st Jazz Music Festival was held in Tashkent; In 1977, 1978, 1984, international festivals of jazz music were held in Fergana. Jazz clubs have been established in these cities, and jazz groups have been established in Bukhara, Navoi and other cities. Among them, the groups led by E. Kalandarov, S. Gilyov (Inter), L. Otabekov (Sato), B. Smetanov (Raduga), G. Kaprielov (Asia) won prizes at international jazz festivals and pop competitions. Currently, among the performers of jazz music, there are the Botir Zokirov variety orchestra (Y. Zhivayev) under the "Uzbeknavo", the "Big Ben" jazz orchestra of the Tashkent State Conservatory, the groups led by Bahadir Murtazayev, G. Bugdanov, A. Khabirkhanov. Samples of Uzbek jazz music are "Sharq suite", "Efsane" and others recorded on gramophone records by "Melodiya" company.⁵

³ ["Jazz Origins in New Orleans – New Orleans Jazz National Historical Park"](#). National Park Service.

⁴ Russkaya sovetskaya estrada // Essays on history. Otv. ed. Ph.D. isk., prof. E.Uvarova. V 3-x T. M., 2012.

⁵ G.M Umarov "History of pop and mass performances" "New century generation" Tashkent 2009

Even now, "Jazz" attracts more and more listeners in our country. Today, this type of music, which is widely used on radio and television, in various holiday programs, has begun to have a significant impact on the minds and minds of millions of people of different ages, not just young people.

Jazz music genre has not been studied by musicologists in our country for years as a special field of research. In particular, the history of Jazz music has not been comprehensively covered, its various directions and trends have not been classified, and the system of special terms has not been scientifically interpreted. Modern musicologists have begun to systematically analyze the process of the emergence of Jazz and the influence of music from other places, as well as the new forms that emerged as a result of this influence.

As you know, the 20th century was a period of sharp renewal in Uzbek music, the emergence of "non-traditional" compositions and new forms of concerts. In this regard, the concept of "jazz" entered the music culture. Initially, it was described as a very wide range of applications. It should be noted that in the reality of modern Uzbekistan, the term "jazz" is used not only in connection with the stage, but also to express a certain trend in music. So, in music culture, the term "Jazz" in a narrow sense refers to music samples based on a certain combination of performance and artistic elements.

It is worth noting that such a view of the spiritual world of each person and society, a deep and comprehensive analysis of the role and importance of such a unique source of power in our lives, which calls a person to a conscious life and perfection, an important truth, a high meaning character means an invincible force.

The most important thing is that today, the art of music has a greater and stronger influence than other forms of art in the development of our young generation in the spirit of high spirituality. We all understand the importance of Jazz art, which attracts the hearts of young people.

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